

Attitudes Towards Vertical Farming Practices among University Students: A Qualitative Inquiry

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Abstract

The growing global population and rapid urbanization necessitate innovative agricultural practices to ensure food security and environmental sustainability. Vertical gardening has emerged as a modern farming technique that utilizes stacked layers and controlled environments to maximize yield within limited spaces. This study explores the attitudes and perceptions of undergraduate students at Horizon Campus, Sri Lanka, toward vertical gardening. A qualitative research design was employed, with data collected through face-to-face semi-structured interviews conducted among 20 students aged 18–24, representing different faculties. The data was analyzed manually using thematic analysis, allowing key patterns to emerge from participant narratives. Findings revealed that while students initially had limited knowledge of vertical gardening, experiential learning opportunities, such as field visits and peer-led demonstrations, significantly enhanced their understanding. Students perceived vertical gardening as a technology-driven, sustainable practice that addresses food security, urban space constraints, and crop diversity. However, participants also identified notable barriers, including high initial costs, limited technical expertise, and reduced adaptability in rural settings. These findings suggest a paradox: vertical gardening is widely acknowledged as beneficial, yet its widespread adoption is hindered by socio-economic and infrastructural challenges. The study concludes that greater emphasis on curriculum integration, policy incentives, and community engagement is needed to promote vertical gardening practices among younger generations. Future research should examine its economic feasibility, scalability in low-income contexts, and integration with emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and smart irrigation systems.

Keywords: *Food security, Student perceptions, Sustainable agriculture, Urban farming, Vertical gardening.*